

EXPERIENCES OF 4PS BENEFICIARIES IN THE CITY OF KORONADAL AND THE LIMITS OF RAWLS' THEORY OF JUSTICE AS FAIRNESS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18787122>

ABSTRACT

The Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps), supervised by the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD), is considered a fitting representation of the concept of justice as fairness, given its goal of giving financial support to extremely poor Filipino families to meet certain development goals of the government. However, a knowledge gap exists between Rawls' Theory of Justice as Fairness and the 4Ps as there has been no knowledge generated by previous studies in applying the theory to interpret the lived experiences of 4Ps beneficiaries. With this, there is a need for an in-depth interpretation of the experiences of the 4Ps beneficiaries, regarding equal basic liberties, access to opportunity, and the difference principle and how these experiences expose the limits in Rawls' criteria of justice. An intrinsic case study was used to gather the experiences of 4Ps beneficiaries within the City of Koronadal and an instrumental case study was used to analyze how these experiences revealed the limits of Rawls' criteria of justice. The experiences reveal practical and theoretical shortcomings in Rawls' theory. Although Rawls argues that social and economic inequalities are acceptable if they benefit the least advantaged, the experiences expose gaps in this ideal, demonstrating the difficulties of implementing these principles in practice. Rawls' theory does not always fully apply to real-world situations, even when certain ideas seem to align. Some experiences only partially match the theory's principles, and others directly challenge them, revealing ongoing difficulties in putting Rawls' theory into practice in actual contexts.

Keywords: *equal basic liberties, access to opportunity, difference principle, criteria of justice, justice as fairness*

INTRODUCTION

Government initiatives aimed at assisting the impoverished, particularly those living in remote regions, were unsuccessful for decades. In an effort for improved social assistance, the administration of Gloria Macapagal Arroyo established the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps), which was tested as a pilot project in a few places in 2008. President Benigno Aquino III began a significant program expansion in 2010 and implemented additional initiatives to improve the program's management and governance after realizing its potential (Orbeta & Paqueo, 2016).

Mahinay et al. (2022) discuss the lived experiences of Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program beneficiaries. First concern was financial instability and inadequacy. The 4Ps was helpful especially in those times that one's family cannot support or provide immediately using the salary one earns. Secondly, government support. The government program has made a great contribution to the past studies of the beneficiaries. It helped in alleviating their financial burdens, particularly regarding education and other expenses. Third, compliance of requirements; the guidelines for compliance. It can be deduced that the beneficiaries encounter challenges in securing requirements. Nationally, the 4Ps operates with the same mechanisms. Thus, it would be highly possible that the experiences of the beneficiaries from different areas would be identical with those experienced by the beneficiaries residing in the City of Koronadal. However, variations may exist because of differing local contexts.

According to the Philippine News Agency (2017), in the implementation of a livelihood initiative for recipients of the flagship Conditional Cash Transfer (CCT) program, the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) in Region 12 allocated around P2 million in 2017. About 200 "poorest of the poor" families in 9 of the City of Koronadal's 27 barangays benefited from the project. The barangays are the following: Topland, Cacub, Sto. Nino, San Jose, Sta. Cruz, Zone 2, Zone 3, Zone 4, and General Paulino Santos.

Furthermore, in collaboration with relevant agencies like the Sustainable Livelihood Program (SLP), a multi-stakeholder program that aims to improve the socioeconomic status of 4Ps beneficiaries and generate further impact on the government's poverty reduction initiatives, the program assists the beneficiaries in developing the skills necessary to run their chosen venture, particularly with regard to its long-term sustainability. Its objective is to assist in the establishment of a sustainable and profitable business that will improve the lives of the recipients (Philippine News Agency, 2017).

The Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program under the supervision of the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) is considered a fitting

representation of the concept of justice as fairness, as seen with its goal of giving financial support to the Filipino families living in extreme poverty to meet certain development goals provided by the government (Talimio & Salagubang, 2019). John Rawls' Theory of Justice as Fairness envisions a society where individuals have equal basic rights and freely cooperate within an egalitarian economic system. In this theory, according to Rawls (1971), "society is interpreted as a cooperative venture for mutual advantage." (p.84). Rawls builds justice as fairness around the idea that people are free and equal, and that society should be fair. For people to live well, social cooperation in some form is needed. However, they are not indifferent about how the advantages and burdens from this cooperation are distributed. His principles reflect the idea that such cooperation must be fair to all individuals who are free and equal (Wenar, 2021). A Rawlsian interpretation is needed in this study, as there is a link between the experiences of the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program beneficiaries and Rawls' Theory of Justice as Fairness, specifically its principles, which is not yet discussed by previous studies. With this, there is a need for an in-depth interpretation of the experiences of the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program beneficiaries, regarding fairness, opportunities, and support in their participation in the program and how these experiences expose the limits in Rawls' criteria of justice. Moreover, the interpretation of these experiences will help in analyzing how the principles of Rawls' Theory of Justice as Fairness operate in real life.

Research Questions

Generally, this study interpreted the experiences of 4Ps beneficiaries regarding fairness, opportunity, and support in their participation in the program and analyzed how these experiences revealed the limits of Rawls' criteria of Justice. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. How do the 4Ps beneficiaries experience fairness or unfairness in their access to rights and liberties within the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program?
2. How do the 4Ps beneficiaries perceive the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program in terms of their access to opportunity?
3. How do the 4Ps beneficiaries describe the ways in which the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program supports or fails to support the least advantaged group?
4. How do the experiences of 4Ps beneficiaries expose the limits of Rawls' criteria of Justice?

METHODOLOGY

Intrinsic, the study of a case such as an individual, specific group, occupation, department, or an organization where the case itself is the main focus in the exploration (Mills et al., 2010) and **instrumental case study**, which seeks to provide insight into a problem or refine a theory in which the case itself in this context is secondary and might be atypical of other cases (Stake, 1995), were utilized to gain valuable empirical insights into the lives of the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program beneficiaries in the City of Koronadal through their experiences as beneficiaries and further understand Rawls'

Theory of Justice as Fairness in terms of its principles such as the equal basic liberties, access to opportunity, and the difference principle.

The study was conducted in the **City of Koronadal, South Cotabato**. According to the LGU of the City of Koronadal, as of 2023, there are 5,034 Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program beneficiaries within the said area. Provided that the paper is a case study, distinctive characteristics were considered, the number of Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program beneficiaries in the City of Koronadal allowed for a more easy and efficient data-gathering process.

With this, the six (6) participants were selected purposefully based on the inclusion criteria or characteristics – *location* (Zone 1, Zone 2, Zone 3, Zone 4, Brgy. GPs, & Brgy. Morales), *length of 4Ps participation* (more than, less than, and exactly three (3) years), *household role* (mother, father, youth), *educational background* (no formal education elementary level, high school level, college level, and vocational), and *income status* (pre-4Ps) (level 1 - survival, level 2 - subsistence, level 3 - self - sufficiency, and recently exited poverty line) – provided by the researchers for the consideration of variability in terms of perspectives. The researchers also utilized the snowball sampling method, which involved asking current participants to help identify future or potential participants.

The data was drawn using a **semi-structured interview guide**, was used to interpret the lived experiences of Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) beneficiaries in Koronadal City to highlight deficiencies in Rawls' criteria of justice. A face-to-face interview was conducted and relevant data were through audio recording, but prior to this, the researchers went through a dry run in order to prepare for contingencies, especially during the interview proper.

The researchers utilized the *thematic analysis* of Braun and Clarke (2006) and Rosala (2022). By utilizing both of these methods, the researchers were able to interpret how the experiences of the 4Ps beneficiaries in the City of Koronadal expose the lackings of Rawls' criteria of Justice.

RESULTS

Experience of Fairness and Unfairness in Access to Rights and Liberties

This subsection provides all the themes and concepts that represent the 4Ps beneficiaries' experiences of fairness or unfairness in terms of accessing rights and liberties.

Table 1
Experiences on Fairness or Unfairness in Accessing Rights and Liberties

Concepts	Themes
Asymmetry in Rights and Duties	Selective Engagement with the Program
Equality of Benefits	Equality experienced as a Beneficiary
Allocation and benefits are based on the size of the family Need-based assistance Provision of benefits and services	Proportional Distribution of Benefits
Transforming taxes into benefits and services. Compliance of Requirements by the Beneficiaries Compliance of the program by the Management	Reciprocity between the Beneficiaries and Institutions
Ignorance by the Management Dishonesty of the Participants	Negligence
Prioritization of the Least Advantaged Groups	Personal and Social Empowerment
Contentment or Satisfaction felt by the beneficiaries.	Program satisfaction by the Beneficiaries
Inequality in the Availment of the Benefits Existing programs are insufficient Inadequacy of the benefits	Limitations of the Program
There should be a combination of satisfaction and consistency.	Consistency ensures Satisfaction

Perceptions of Access to Opportunity within the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program

This subsection provides all the themes and concepts that represent the 4Ps beneficiaries' perception of the 4Ps in terms of their access to opportunity.

Table 2
4Ps Beneficiaries' Perception of the 4Ps in terms of their Access to Opportunity

Concepts	Themes
Creating opportunities through active participation	Creating opportunities through active participation
Opportunities are accessible for the beneficiaries Additional resources for Education 4Ps program helps in improving the performance of the children	Increased accessibility to opportunities
Prioritization of the health of the least advantaged groups	Easily accessed health opportunities
4Ps' support as an addition to the availability of resources	4Ps as a support system to the beneficiaries
Individuals are Empowered through Socialization Empowerment of 4Ps beneficiaries	Personal and Social Empowerment
Job Opportunities were accessible for the beneficiaries	Accessibility of Job opportunities
Limitation of benefits and services Insufficient support in sustaining one's needs	Opportunity is limited
4Ps opportunity creates beneficiary satisfaction	Beneficiary Satisfaction through 4Ps opportunity

Experiences of Support among the Least Advantaged Group

This subsection provides all the themes and concepts that represent the ways in which the 4Ps supports or fails to support the least advantaged group.

Table 3
Ways in which the program supports or fails to support

Concepts	Themes
Perceived Sufficiency or Adequacy of Support	Perceived Sufficiency or Adequacy of Support

Confidence in the assistance that 4Ps provides	Trust and Confidence in the Program
Support is insufficient in sustaining one's needs	Limitations of the Program
Sustainable support through long-term assistance	Sustainability of Support by the Program
Adherence of the management with the requirements and schedule	Procedural Delivery of Service
Beneficiary-centric avenue for assistance Prioritization of the Least Advantaged Groups	Personal and Social Empowerment
Inaccuracy of Support due to Uncertainty created by diverse needs	Uncertainty of Diverse Needs leads to Inaccuracy of Support
Compliance of Requirements by the Beneficiaries	Reciprocity between the Beneficiaries and Institutions

The Limits of Rawls' Criteria of Justice as Revealed Through Beneficiaries' Experiences

The experiences of 4Ps beneficiaries highlighted both practical and conceptual limits in Rawls's criteria of justice. While his theory holds the idea that social and economic inequalities are justifiable if they are to the benefit of the least advantaged, the realities faced by the beneficiaries shows the gaps in this ideal, particularly regarding equal basic liberties, access to opportunity, and the difference principle, highlighting the challenges that arise when applying these principles in real-world contexts.

Theoretically, it amplifies the relevance of Rawls' principles—equal basic liberties, fair equality of opportunity, and the difference principle—in evaluating social justice and welfare policies. It also highlights the need in considering the interplay between individual responsibility as beneficiaries and institutional support, emphasizing that justice requires fair cooperation and appropriately structured inequalities to benefit the least advantaged, as argued by Rawls.

Practically, it points to challenges in policy implementation, such as ensuring eligibility integrity, addressing diverse and unmet needs, and promoting active participation to avoid dependency. It suggests that social programs must balance providing adequate material support with encouraging beneficiaries' contributions to maintain fairness.

DISCUSSION

Experiences on Fairness or Unfairness in Accessing Rights and Liberties

Although the principle ensures equal rights and fair treatment, the lived experiences of the beneficiaries show gaps where responsibilities and mutual cooperation fail to materialize. This imbalance challenges the idea that everyone can equally exercise their rights and participate in the cooperative schemes of society, thereby restricting genuine justice. This selective engagement undermines the delicate balance that Rawls envisions between rights and responsibilities, exposing the tension between the theory's moral ideal and the complexities of reality. Ultimately, this points out that achieving genuine justice requires not only equal liberties but also strong and effective mechanisms that can foster accountability and shared responsibility within society.

4Ps Beneficiaries' Perception of the Pantawid Pilipino Program in terms of their Access to Opportunity

Based on the lived experiences of the beneficiaries, some of them exploit the program by concealing their status causing the program management to unknowingly grant unfair advantage which undermine those individuals who are genuinely disadvantaged and violating the principle that opportunities should be equally and fairly available to all. Access or participation to other livelihood programs were limited due to the beneficiaries' membership in the program, presented in the limitations of opportunities. With this, it proves that institutions prioritizing the least advantaged groups in society may also hinder these groups from accessing new and more opportunities due to the fact that other program performing the same functions as the 4Ps do not allow 4Ps beneficiaries to avail benefits from these programs solely because of their membership in the Pantawid Familyang Pilipino Program. Moreover, the failure of the management to accurately verify the actual circumstances of the beneficiaries results to ignorance and dishonesty which allow inequalities to persist without being checked. These lapses contradict Rawls' vision of institutions that ensure opportunities are truly available based on actual need and merit which reveal significant gaps between Rawls' ideal conception of justice and the practical reality.

Ways in which the Program Supports or Fails to Support

Although the 4Ps program prioritizes the least advantaged by giving benefits and support that are targeted for the beneficiaries, there are instances that the diverse and complex circumstances of beneficiaries can prevent the program from fully addressing each of the beneficiaries' needs and sometimes causes failure to adequately accommodate those varied situations. The uncertainty in understanding the different needs of beneficiaries leads inaccuracy of support. This shows that even when institutions provide for the least advantaged, in this sense the 4Ps beneficiaries, uncertainty and inaccuracy in support still arise from a lack of clear understanding of the diverse needs of the beneficiaries which can lead to ineffective assistance. There is also the tendency to foster dependency or reliance on aid rather than empowerment as some beneficiaries

become dependent on the benefit they receive and do not seek alternative source income which is in conflict with Rawls' ideal concept of justice that promotes self-sufficiency, revealing the limits between the ideal and the complex social reality.

Conclusions

Ultimately, the lived experiences of Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) beneficiaries underscore the limitations of Rawls' Theory of Justice as Fairness when applied to real-world social welfare initiatives. While Rawls' principle of equal basic liberties, fair equality of opportunity, and the difference principle set an ideal framework for reciprocal cooperation and mutual advantage, they falter in taking into consideration the tendencies of human behavior such as selective engagement, dishonesty, and dependency. The beneficiaries' failure to uphold their responsibilities which was evident in the minimal participation during clean-up drives yet full attendance during the release of benefits, undermines the balance between rights and responsibilities, while being dishonest about their circumstances and the oversight of the program's management distort fair access to opportunities, enabling unjust advantages to some at the expense of those who are truly in need. Similarly, even though the program's uniform distribution of cash grants is intended for the least advantaged, it inadequately addresses diverse needs and foster reliance instead of empowerment as beneficiaries like P3 and P6 highlight the clash between standardized aid and personal circumstances.

This gap exposes Rawls' critical oversight: his criteria assume rational, cooperative agents within idealized institutions while neglecting the complexities of human psychology, decision-making, and contextual needs in practice. In the Philippine context, institutional prioritization of the least advantages clash with opportunistic actions of some beneficiaries and the inherent multifaceted nature of poverty which results in inefficiencies that perpetuate inequality instead of solving it. Therefore, achieving true justice as fairness demands not only theoretical principles but adaptive mechanisms such as robust verification and tailored interventions or support that can bridge the gap between Rawls' idea of justice and the unpredictable reality of human tendencies and experiences.

Recommendations

For the legislators, the application of Rawls' Theory of Justice as Fairness in social programs implies a need for initiatives that do not foster long-term dependency among the beneficiaries. Programs targeting the least advantaged must consider incorporating mechanisms that promote self-reliance and sustainable development beyond immediate assistance.

For the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program, these findings imply that resource distribution must be more tailored to the unique needs and circumstances of each individual or family. A one-size-fits-all approach risks inefficiency and unmet needs, highlighting the importance of flexibility and responsiveness in program implementation.

The effectiveness and fairness of the program heavily depends on the integrity of assessment tools like the Social Welfare and Development Indicator (SWDI) and so it implies a pressing need to enhance the assessment processes by the program to prevent dishonesty and manipulation which creates unfairness when it comes to the qualification of the members.

Additionally, promoting the development of independent income sources among beneficiaries highlights the need to focus on empowerment—relying solely on the assistance alone is not enough to achieve lasting poverty alleviation. The program should include measures that can help the beneficiaries maintain financial stability even after completing the program to encourage self-sufficiency and minimize dependency.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers adhered to the ethical standards and protocol provided by the Ethics Review Board and the regional office of the Department of Social Welfare Development in the City of Koronadal before conducting the interviews. The study “Justice in Practice: A Rawlsian Interpretation of the Experiences of Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program Beneficiaries’ in the City of Koronadal” has received a notice of Panel Action from the NDMU Ethics Review Board, on June 30, 2025 and acknowledges receipt of the researchers request and the accompanying supporting documents that underwent a full review. The Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program Beneficiaries, who were the participants, were informed and chosen by the DSWD from Region XII in the City of Koronadal and approached by the researchers who explained the study’s purpose, procedures, risk and benefits. Moreover, the participants received a letter of an informed consent form before the interview was conducted and were given time to read and ask questions.

In order to minimize these risks, the researchers utilized an informed consent emphasizing the safety measures for the participants and with the guidance of the agency in charge of the 4Ps beneficiaries residing in the City of Koronadal, the participants were able to feel secure in participating in the study. The researchers were also prepared to offer support and resources to address any negative emotional responses. This includes providing access to counseling services or other support systems. It was also stated that their identities would be kept private and all responses would be used for academic purposes only and treated with utmost confidentiality.

Additionally, to minimize the study’s negative impact on the participants’ well – being, the researchers emphasized to the participants the ethical considerations and safety measures that were followed during the accomplishment of the study. Moreover, the researchers have coordinated with the agency in charge of the 4Ps beneficiaries residing in the City of Koronadal for the facilitation and identification of the participants while ensuring that the researchers followed the safety protocols needed to ensure the safety and well-being of the participants. The participants had the freedom to leave or withdraw from participating in the interview with or without explanation. The participants also had the right to request that any of the information they share will not be used in the

study if they so desire. Also, the researchers demonstrated that the ethical issues of consent, risk of harm, and confidentiality were clearly defined.

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